

Microcontroller Based EOG Guided Wheel Chair

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Abstract : A new cost effective, eye controlled method was introduced to guide and control a wheel chair for disable people, based on Electro-oculography (EOG). The guidance and control is effected by eye ball movements within the socket. The system consists of a standard electric wheelchair with an on-board microcontroller system attached. EOG is a new technology to sense the eye signals for eye movements and these signals are captured using electrodes, signal processed such as amplification, noise filtering, and then given to microcontroller which drives the motors attached with wheel chair for propulsion. This technique could be very useful in applications such as mobility for handicapped and paralyzed persons.

Keywords : electro-oculography, microcontroller, signal processing, wheelchair

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